

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-2-52-IG-5% rac	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	0
Vial:	6	Acq. Method Set:	5%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 2 52
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	276.0nm
Run Time:	16.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 276.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	4/25/2022 7:38:10 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 7:23:47 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	11.930	6087301	49.38	330245
2	13.118	6239772	50.62	298909

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-2-161-IG-5% asy	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	0
Vial:	119	Acq. Method Set:	5%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 2 161
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	276.0nm
Run Time:	16.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 276.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	6/23/2022 12:01:20 CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 19:16:35 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	13.627	1081886	3.91	51986
2	14.879	26601912	96.09	1160802